

Analysis of Customer Satisfaction during Online Purchase

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Abstract

Online shopping turned out to be a current trend for shopping for customer now. People across the globe are now exploring the area of online shopping more and more. The online shopping experience help the customer to explore their product, compare the same across various online shopping domain and hassle free shopping without experiencing traffic jam and lack of time. This entire process of saving of time and ease in shopping became the most dominant factor for increasing popularity of online shopping. The current research attempted to find out the outlook of customers towards online shopping and the factors that affect the online purchase. With the rapid penetration of Internet, online shopping has developed quickly in our country as a fresh way for shopping. Considering this as an opportunity many global retailers are creating better platforms for customers to enrich their shopping experience.

The research adopted survey method to understand customer perception towards online shopping and the tool used for survey is questionnaire. The survey is done across students as well as working professional group to measure and understand their perception for online shopping. Findings of this research will highlight on the key issues that will primarily drive customer satisfaction. The study revealed that factors like website design, payment security; Ease of shopping, accurate product information; price and delivery services has optimistic impact on purchaser satisfaction

Keywords: Consumer satisfaction, Online / Web - based shopping,

Introduction

Internet is an unusual thing that rules the digital world in recent time. According to report of Singapore based digital agency which is known for its APAC reports states that "India's digital landscape is growing very fast and the major proliferation of internet is through mobile devices. Due to easily and well accessed internet the usage of the same is huge. The report also figures out statistics of somewhat 243.2 million internet users and 106 million active users in India. Besides these India is also acting as proliferate base for mobile usage which also indirectly increased the use of various web based apps through the device. 70% of the page views in internet are accessed through mobile. Thus internet is truly ruling the country's heart and nerves. The internet offers various benefits and offers to consumers that drive them more towards online shopping. Online/web based shopping offers fast and rapid access to variety of product related information in turn saving consumers time, effort and money also enhances the purchase experience and provide the best quality of the product at best price. Thus there is an immense shift in people's interest for online shopping due to convenience in shopping, varied options available online, easily comparable prices. This rapid increase of online customers' base point towards the area of customer/consumer satisfaction which acts as an important aspect in online purchase, as that will directly influence the purchase and re-purchase decision of customer. Majority of fulfilled customers usually go for re-purchase, because they were happy with the purchase and also satisfied with the performance of their purchased product. Customer satisfaction is influenced by number of factors. Various researches have been conducted to categorize different variables/factors that affect online shopping. Some of them are discussed thoroughly during reviewing the literatures. Thus in order to expand and influence customer and improve the business performance customer satisfaction is a key ingredient and the retailers doing business online must have a clear understanding on the various factors that positively influence customer satisfaction. With regard to this, the present research

aims to identify key factors that positively affect customer satisfaction and statistically validate the same through performing multivariate statistical tools.

The aim of this study is

- To understand the aspects that leads towards customer/consumer satisfaction.
- To establish and validate that the determined factors positively affect customer satisfaction.

Theoretical Background and Literature Review

The European Public Administration Network (EUPAN) suggested through a model that customer/consumer satisfaction is a key area with regard to any services we provide to a customer/consumer. If the experience of the shopping and the services offered greatly exceeds the expectations of customer, then satisfaction will be elevated. Many researchers in their research discussed the fact that a customer has to be satisfied with their preliminary online shopping experience before considering the purchase of goods and services online or for making re-purchase decision. Some studies specifically tried to understand and identify the background of customer satisfaction during web-based shopping. The outcome of these researches clearly species that the most important attributes that primarily drives the customer satisfaction is the safety and security during the purchase. If the customer has better experience with regard to services provided by the retailer online then also satisfaction escalates (Shankar et al. 2003).

In addition, researcher across different domains documented three classes of variables that influence client satisfaction towards online shopping. These are skill factors, shopping factors and merchandise factors. The various literatures reviewed and considered significantly give emphasis on the following features as principle areas that drive customer/consumer/client satisfaction. The factors identified were ease in accessibility of website, convenience in shopping, safety measures, information quality, payment

method, e-service quality, product quality, product variety, and delivery service.

Lee and Lin (2005) through their research envisaged that ease in accessibility of website highly controls the overall customer satisfaction as ease in handling and accessing things in a particular e-commerce websites increase the satisfaction level in customer. Cyr (2008) during his research work proposed that ease in accessing websites, ease in navigation of products in website have a positive influence on online shopping behaviour and customer satisfaction. Various literatures also demonstrated about security issues during online shopping. It was further discussed that ability of online portal to protect customer's personal information helps to build trust and enhances the satisfaction level. (Elliot & Fowell, 2000) discussed that as consciousness on security risk declines the satisfaction is expected to increase. Thus in other words, strong security attribute is directly proportional with the degree of customer satisfaction. The other major factor that attributes towards customer satisfaction is accuracy of information about product in the e-commerce websites. Accurate information about the product and quality has significant effect on consumer satisfaction in online shopping. Also consumers doing their online shopping look forward to websites to provide for secure payment, and maintain the privacy of their online communication (Franzak et al., 2001). Besides this, Liu et al. (2008) highlighted in his research that more of information regarding product and product quality improves the customer satisfaction during online shopping. Findings of the research clearly reveals the fact that there is a noteworthy effect of all e-service quality on customers' satisfaction towards online shopping. (Jung-Hwan & Chung, 2010).

Other studies in this area of online purchase identified that variety of products and with comparatively little fewer prices create a positive impact on the shopping experience which further leads to customer/consumer/client satisfaction. The other predominant factor that affects the online shopping experience and is indirectly related to customer satisfaction is logistics related issues. Delivery of the product on or before the expected delivery creates positive impact on customer. In the same manner delayed delivery has a negative effect on satisfaction. Findings from a diversity of researches indicate that on-time/ before-time delivery has noteworthy influence on customer satisfaction and it leads to a greater variance in satisfaction.

Thus through an elaborate review of existing literatures on customer satisfaction through online shopping it is quite evident that customer satisfaction is dependent on many factors. For the present study we will consider some of those factors which majorly influence the customer satisfaction and through that will try to establish the research. The factors identified through literature survey and considered for this research are

- a. Website design.
- b. Payment security.
- c. Ease of shopping.
- d. Accurate Product Information.
- e. Price.
- f. Delivery services.

Hypothesis

From the literature study hypotheses developed for this study which are listed below -

H1: Website design influence consumer satisfaction during online shopping.

H2: Payment security influence customer satisfaction during online shopping.

H3: Ease of shopping influence customer satisfaction during online shopping.

H4: Product Information influence customer satisfaction during online shopping.

H5: Price has influence on customer satisfaction during online shopping.

H6: Delivery services have positive impact on customer satisfaction during online shopping.

Methodology

This comes under a correlational study which attempts to examine the statistical relationship between online customer satisfaction which is dependent on few independent variables such as Website design, payment security, Ease of shopping, product information, and price and delivery services. The sample for this study consists of students and working professionals. Convenience sampling is chosen as the sampling design in this study. This would help in doing exploratory study in a better way and it is the quickest way of getting information. A total of 150 questionnaires were circulated at random to students and working professional and 120 responses were gathered. The questionnaire comprises of 25 close ended questions divided into two sections - section A & section B. Section -A details about demographic information and section-B indicates questions related to information which measures online customer satisfaction. The questions consisted of a range of responses of strongly agree to disagree, on a 5 point Likert scale. The question incorporated in the survey tool includes all of the variables that were considered as important factors for determining customer satisfaction.

Results & Discussion

Table 1 illustrates the demographic profile of respondents. The demographic profile is consists of gender, age, education level, monthly income & marital status.

Table 1: Demographic profile

Demographic Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	69	58
	Female	51	42
Age	21 - 30 years old	31	26
	31 - 40 years old	65	54
	41 -50 years old	24	20
Qualification	Degree	50	42
	Master	60	50
	PhD	10	8
Marital Status	Single	66	55
	Married	52	43
	Divorce	2	2
Monthly Income	Less than 3,0000	77	64
	Between 3 lakhs – 5 lakhs	30	25
	Above 5 lakhs	13	11

Reliability Analysis

The reliability analysis is done through Cronbach alpha test highlighted in the Table 2 below. The reliability coefficient (Cronbach Alpha) of the variables goes above the minimum acceptable level of 0.70 which depicts that the questions induced in the questionnaire are reliable and qualifies the minimum acceptance.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis

Variables	Number of items	Number of item included	Cronbach Alpha
Website design	3	3	0.711
Payment security	3	3	0.701
Ease of shopping	5	5	0.733
Accurate product information	5	5	0.836
Price	2	2	0.753
Delivery services	2	2	0.789

Multiple Regression Analysis

The result of multiple regression analysis is shown below in Table 3(a) and Table 3(b). The Tolerance ranges from 0.598 to 0.816, which are all larger than 0.10 (standard value), and the VIF value ranges from 1.226 to 1.671, which are all less than 5 as referred by Hair et al., 2006. Thus, it clearly indicates that the problem of multicollinearity does not exist among the considered independent variables.

Table 3a. Model summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	Significance
1	0.735	0.540	0.254	31.272	0.000

Table 3b: Regression Analysis - ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	613.942	6	102.32	38.90	.000
Residual	920.154	350	2.63		
Total	1534.096	356			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Website design, payment security, Ease of shopping, accurate product information, price and delivery services

b. **Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction**

Table 3c. Regression analysis – Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	Collinearity Statistics			
	B	Std. Error	β	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	2.115	.904		2.325	.015		
Website Design	.066	.022	.126	2.765	.005	.744	1.209
Payment security	.087	.033	.134	2.863	.003	.766	1.269
Ease of shopping	.077	.039	.119	2.077	.037	.698	1.661
Product Info	.158	.078	.097	2.018	.045	.762	1.389
Price	.089	.046	.093	1.988	.048	.776	1.298
Delivery service	.178	.040	.223	4.529	.000	.624	1.638

a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction

The p values of the independent variables are less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the research concludes that all the considered independent variables i.e. Website design, payment security, Ease of shopping, product information, price and delivery services influence the customer satisfaction. This means that the hypotheses proposed in the research are supported by the analysis. Based on the Coefficients table (Table 3c), the multiple regression equation formed is shown below:

$$\text{Customer satisfaction} = 2.115 + 0.066 (\text{website design}) + 0.087 (\text{payment security}) + 0.077(\text{ease of shopping}) + 0.158 (\text{product info}) + 0.089 (\text{price}) + 0.178 (\text{delivery service})$$

The Standardized Coefficients column explains the strength among variables. The statuses of the variables based on strength are as follows:

- Delivery service (0.223)
- Payment security (0.134)
- Website design (0.126)
- Ease of shopping (0.119)
- Product Info (.097)
- Price (.093)

From the standardized coefficients values above it can be concluded that the most important variable that affects customer satisfaction very positively during online purchase is the delivery services and the second most powerful variable is security during payment. Rest other variables follows after the two.

Based on Table 3 (a), the study also concludes that the website design, payment security, Ease of shopping, accurate product information, price and delivery services accounts for 54 percent of customer satisfaction.

Conclusion

This researcher attempted through this paper to conduct a decisive study of six determinants derived from elaborative literature i.e. that website design, payment security, Ease of shopping, accurate product information; price and on- time delivery services. The research clearly depicts that all these determinants influence positively on consumer/customer/client satisfaction from the facet of online shopping in different e commerce sites.

In addition, the research findings provides insight on the fact that the retailers in this space should consider on how to get better performance to increase the customer satisfaction level and standout in the highly competitive business in online environment. The retailers should re-evaluate all these six variables that highly impact customer satisfaction and should initiate and re-construct their strategies accordingly to sustain in the extremely competitive business environment. These variables are actually acting as customer feedback while online shopping, what exactly they feel and what they need while shopping online. This study will act as an important part for evaluating and enhancing their performance.

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